

1 **Genomic information and metafounders in Latxa genetic evaluations.** Granada-Tajada.
2 Including genomic information into genetic evaluations yields more precise estimates of
3 breeding values in sheep breeding programs. Moreover, new tools have been developed to
4 model missing pedigree based on genomic data by metafounders implementation. The
5 possible benefits of genomics were analysed into the real data available at Latxa breeding
6 program, comparing genetic and genomic evaluations by cross-validation. Predictions with
7 consistent accuracy and no gain in accuracy by genomic information inclusion were found.

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9 **GENOMIC INFORMATION AND METAFFOUNDERS IN LATXA GENETIC**
10 **EVALUATIONS**

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12 **Exploring the inclusion of genomic information and metafounders in Latxa dairy sheep**
13 **genetic evaluations**

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ABSTRACT

27 The availability of genomic marker panels has made possible more precise estimates of
28 breeding values. Sheep breeding programs are implementing genomic selection (GS). In
29 Latxa dairy sheep breed, a previous study using pre-corrected data and small number of
30 genotyped animals did not show clear advantage of GS. So, the objective of the present study
31 was to ascertain the possible benefits of GS for Latxa breed, based on more data than before
32 and using better tools, in particular Single Step Genomic BLUP (ssGBLUP) using
33 metafounders to model missing pedigree. Goodness of prediction of pedigree and genomic
34 evaluations was analysed by cross-validation comparing predictions of young rams using
35 whole and partial (truncated) data sets. The results showed that with the current available
36 data, genetic and genomic evaluations have the same accuracy. Contrary to the previous
37 study, predictions were nearly unbiased, what shows the advantage of using ssGBLUP.
38 However, genomic information did not yield more precise evaluations. This could be
39 explained by the small number of sibs in the young rams.

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KEY WORDS

42 Genomic selection, cross-validation, Latxa breed, dairy sheep

INTRODUCTION

43

44 The Latxa is a dairy sheep breed from the Western Pyrenees. Two strains are distinguished,
45 mainly according to the skin colour, the black strain Latxa Cara Negra (**LCN**) and the red
46 strain Latxa Cara Rubia (**LCR**). Moreover, the black strain is divided in two geographic areas
47 with slight morphological differences: Basque Country (**LCNEUS**) and Navarre (**LCNNAF**).
48 Three separate breeding programs exist for the 3 strains. Currently milk yield, milk
49 composition and udder morphology traits are being selected. Presently, the breeding program
50 is well implemented and shows consolidated results with an annual genetic gain between
51 0.19-0.23 standard deviations, depending on the strain.

52 With the development of genomics, Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs) are being used
53 to implement genomic selection (GS) in several livestock species. In small ruminants GS is
54 less frequent and generally gains in accuracy introducing GS are small (Mrode et al., 2018).
55 Regarding dairy sheep, empirical studies to analyse accuracies of genomic predictions in the
56 Lacaune breed, showed that Genomic Estimated Breeding Value (GEBV) for milk yield was
57 0.15 more accurate than (pedigree-based) Estimated Breeding Value (EBV) (Duchemin et al.,
58 2012; Baloche et al., 2014b). An experiment (selecting rams using either GEBV or EBV)
59 confirmed the gain in annual genetic gain (AGG) (Baloche et al., 2014a).

60 Because generation interval is already short (4 years), the implementation of GS in dairy
61 sheep depends critically on the ability to select accurately young rams. Modelling genomic
62 versus classic scheme showed that AGG could increase up to 51.7% with genomic
63 information, with a reference population of at least 1000 animals (Shumbusho et al., 2013). A
64 performing GS scheme in Lacaune was conceived and implemented (Buisson et al., 2014).
65 This scheme yields extra 10-20% of gain in AGG and 20-40% reduction of artificial
66 insemination (AI) rams. The latter is important because in progeny-testing dairy sheep
67 schemes using fresh semen, a large number of rams are waiting (and consuming resources)

68 for first crop after their first use on AI, whereas a genomic scheme could avoid this waiting
69 period based on breeding values estimated with a higher precision. Therefore, by modifying
70 the management towards a GS scheme there could be less rams in the AI centre, reducing
71 costs and no loss of genetic diversity.

72 In Western Pyrenees breeds, the implementation of GS was studied for the first time in 2014.
73 Legarra et al. (2014), carried out a study with six breeds of dairy sheep, including the two
74 strains of French Manech (which is a breed highly related to Latxa), Spanish Latxa with three
75 strains and Basco-Béarnaise. Results showed a gain in accuracy when genomic information
76 was included (0.11 for Manech Tête Noire, 0.16 for Manech Tête Rousse and 0.06 for Basco-
77 Béarnaise), therefore GS started in 2017. However, the studies of Legarra et al. (2014) did not
78 show a clear advantage of GS in Latxa. Increases in accuracy using GEBVs were -0.18 (a
79 deterioration) for LCNEUS, 0.30 for LCR and 0.04 for LCNNAF. Genomic predictions were
80 generally less biased than pedigree ones. However, some results were difficult to understand.
81 For instance, for LCR EBVs had almost 0 accuracy, which does not agree with the observed
82 genetic progress that the breeding program. Predictions in some strains were frankly biased.
83 Authors attributed these problems to poor genotyping (*e.g.* many “holes” across the years)
84 and perhaps to poor modelling (pseudo-Single Step GBLUP was used, using Daughter Yield
85 Deviations). Also, there was a weak relation between genotyped rams in training and
86 validation groups.

87 Since 2014, the Latxa breeding program has collected more phenotypic and pedigree data and
88 has genotyped all the new males used in the last years in AI. Also, new developments in
89 evaluation, like Single Step GBLUP (ssGBLUP) which enables to use phenotypes of both
90 animals with and without genotypes, yield better predictions (Legarra et al., 2009;
91 Christensen and Lund, 2010). New methods in validation of results (Method LR - Legarra and
92 Reverter, 2018) may yield more objective measures of predictive ability. Furthermore, the

93 metafounders (**MF**) theory (Legarra et al., 2015) provides a more coherent framework for
94 genomic evaluation theory Garcia-Baccino et al., 2017; Meyer et al., 2018; Bradford et al.,
95 2019). In essence, they model missing pedigrees using populations (like genetic groups) but
96 these populations are of finite size and related according to observed genomic relationships of
97 their descendants.

98 Thus, the objective of this work is to take a new look, with more data and better tools, into the
99 effect of including genomic information into the genetic evaluations of LCR and LCNEUS
100 strains. The LCNNAF population was not included in this study due to the small increase in
101 number of genotyped rams.

102 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

103 *Phenotypic and Pedigree Data*

104 All data came from the Latxa Breeders' Associations' Confederation (CONFELAC). The full
105 data set included in this study comprised 639517 lactations and 263308 animals in pedigree of
106 LCNEUS and 392109 lactations and 150185 animals in pedigree of LCR. The evaluated trait
107 was 120-d standardized milk yield whose heritability is 0.18 and 0.22 for LCNEUS and LCR,
108 respectively. More details about phenotypic and pedigree data are shown in Table 1.

109 Because of the frequent use of natural mating with several rams, the breeding program only
110 accepts filiations for AI rams. Also, there are a number of unknown dams – mainly in flocks
111 entering the breeding scheme. As a result, based on the average of the full data set, 31 % of
112 the ewes with milk records have unknown sire and dam, even though since 2000 this
113 percentage decreases to 21 %. In addition, importation of semen from the French breed
114 Manech Tête Rousse (**MTR**) to the Spanish LCR scheme has been sporadic since the 90's
115 and systematic since 2010. The ancestries of those MTR individuals included into LCR
116 pedigree are unknown, and because the French breeding scheme started earlier, they should

117 not be considered genetically equal to Spanish unknown contemporary individuals as was
118 reported by Ugarte et al. (1996).

119 To palliate for these two kinds of missing pedigree, Genetic Groups (Quaas, 1988) are used
120 for BLUP. However, the use of genetic groups in ssGBLUP is problematic (Misztal et al.,
121 2013) and we decided to use MF (Legarra et al., 2015) to model missing pedigree. The
122 assignment of MF was done looking for a balanced number on individuals in each MF group,
123 considering the year of birth and the Spanish or French origin of the progeny. With this aim,
124 for LCNEUS 11 MF groups were defined, from 1985 to 2015 every 3 years; and for LCR 14
125 MF groups, from 1985 to 2015 every 3 years for Spanish progeny and every 9 years for
126 French origin.

127 ***Genotypic Data***

128 Using stored (for old ones) and recent DNA samples, AI rams were genotyped with the
129 OvineSNP50 BeadChip (Illumina Inc., San Diego, CA). As quality control, animals with call
130 rate <0.90 and parent-progeny Mendelian conflicts ($<5\%$) were eliminated. For SNPs,
131 markers with heritability estimate of gene content <0.98 were removed (Forneris et al., 2015),
132 as well as those with call rate <0.97 , MAF <0.05 , monomorphic or located in sexual
133 chromosomes. After quality control 780 rams (353 LCNEUS and 427 LCR) and 39159 and
134 38168 effective SNPs for LCNEUS and LCR respectively, were considered for genomic
135 evaluations. Regarding the previous study (Legarra et al., 2014), this work includes 178 new
136 genotyped individuals (80 LCNEUS and 98 LCR) corresponding to the rams entering the AI
137 centre from 2010 to 2014. Genotyping was irregular during the first years, but from 2011 all
138 the rams entering the AI centre have been genotyped, which enables a more balanced and
139 stronger data structure. The distribution of genotyped rams by year of birth is shown in Figure
140 1.

141 ***Estimation of (Genomic) Breeding Values***

142 To obtain (G)EBVs the Blupf90 family programs (Misztal et al., 2002) were used, using
143 either pedigree-based BLUP or ssGBLUP (Legarra et al., 2009; Christensen and Lund, 2010).
144 In both cases the model for the milk yield included: flock-year-season, parity number-age at
145 lambing, number of alive lambs born, and interval between lambing and the first test day as
146 fixed effects and permanent environmental and additive genetic (Legarra et al., 2005) with
147 MF as random effects. Strains were evaluated separately as they do not interbreed. The MF
148 approach considers relationships within and across base populations. These relationships are
149 summarised in a matrix Γ , which was estimated using the GLS method in Garcia-Baccino et
150 al. (2017). Supplementary Table 1 and 2 show Γ estimates for each breed.

151 *Goodness of Prediction*

152 The goodness of prediction of pedigree and genomic evaluations was analysed by cross-
153 validation using the LR method (Legarra and Reverter, 2018). This method measures biases
154 and accuracies from global changes in (G)EBVs of candidates to selection from a “partial”
155 (1984-2014) to a “whole” (1984-2017) data set. We chose a set of validation individuals,
156 considering genotyped AI rams born into the last 3 cohorts of the partial data set (between
157 2012 and 2014). The details of rams’ distribution across validation and training group are
158 described in Table 2. These animals were not progeny tested in the partial data set and have at
159 least 10 daughters with lactations in the whole data set. First, GEBVs were estimated in whole
160 and partial data sets using ssGBLUP. Second, EBVs were estimated in whole and partial data
161 sets using BLUP. Statistics of bias, slope and correlation $\rho_{w,p}$ for validation individuals were
162 calculated from the linear regression of GEBV estimated with whole data on GEBV estimated
163 with partial data and from the linear regression of EBV estimated with whole data on EBV
164 estimated with partial data.

165 Bias defines the capacity to predict average value of candidates to selection and 0 would mean
166 unbiasedness and is measured as the difference of average (G)EBVs across whole and partial;

167 slope could be taken as a measure of the dispersion of (G)EBVs of candidates to selection,
168 which should be 1, and it was obtained as the slope of the regression of (G)EBV estimated
169 with whole data on (G)EBV estimated with partial data. Finally, we estimated the correlation
170 $\rho_{w,p}$ (G)EBV from partial data with (G)EBV from whole data, which could be understood as
171 the relative increase of accuracy from partial to whole data. For instance, a value of 0.9 means
172 that (G)EBVs with partial data (with parent average or genomic information, but not
173 offspring) were almost equal to (G)EBVs with whole data (with progeny). In that sense, high
174 values are expected for genomic prediction, and low values for pedigree-based prediction.
175 Due to the small size and selected character of validation groups, a bootstrap procedure with
176 1000 iterations was implemented, to sample with replacement the validation individuals and
177 calculate the bootstrap distribution of bias, slope and $\rho_{w,p}$ and their differences (*e.g.* the
178 distribution of bias in ssGBLUP minus bias in BLUP).
179 The relationship between and within training and validation group is known to be important
180 for genetic prediction (Pszczola et al., 2012). For both breeds a high proportion of validation
181 individuals have sire and maternal grandsire in the training group. In addition, around half of
182 the validation rams have their sire genotyped, whereas one third of the maternal grandsires are
183 genotyped. In the case of non-genotyped relatives GS could still work, but with less
184 advantage than with genotyped relatives (Pszczola et al., 2011). The described pedigree
185 relationships (shown in Table 3 and Table 4) may not be optimal, but comparing with the
186 previous study (Legarra et al., 2014) the reference population is larger and more related to the
187 candidates to selection.

188 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

189 Table 5 shows the main results of the cross-validation using the LR method. The bias of
190 validation individuals was small, not significantly different from 0, and very similar in
191 pedigree and genomic evaluations (the difference of estimated biases is 4.21 ± 2.63 and

192 4.08±2.55, for LCNEUS and LCR, respectively). Note that these differences are expressed in
193 litres, and the genetic standard deviation is 17.52 and 21.31 for LCNEUS and LCR,
194 respectively. Across both breeds, BLUP had slopes closer to 1 than ssGBLUP, and LCR was
195 significantly different from 1. Although the use of selectively genotyped individuals could
196 affect the results (Vitezica et al., 2011), experience in dairy cattle and other dairy sheep
197 breeds (VanRaden et al. 2009; Baloche et al., 2014b) show that genotyping selected males
198 does not result in bias because these animals will become average animals in the next
199 generation. Moreover, a possible explanation for LCR lower estimates, that is hard to verify,
200 is that imported MTR rams are a selected population and this was not correctly accounted for.
201 Regarding the estimator of accuracies, $\rho_{w,p}$, predictions based on pedigree information had
202 moderate-high $\rho_{w,p}$, 0.55 and 0.50 for LCNEUS and LCR, respectively. When predictions
203 were based also in genomic information, $\rho_{w,p}$ was slightly higher, 0.56 and 0.51 for LCNEUS
204 and LCR, respectively. The comparison of BLUP and ssGBLUP shows that the inclusion of
205 genotypes did not increase neither decrease the accuracy of predictions for any of the breeds.
206 Comparing the current results with the previous ones (Legarra et al., 2014), in general
207 predictions are more consistent, indicating that breeding values are more correctly estimated.
208 Biases are lower and with considerably smaller standard errors, which were remarkably high
209 in the previous study (around 60 for LCNEUS and 100 for LCR). The current slopes of the
210 regression are for both methodologies closer to 1 than previous ones which were around 0.30
211 in both LCNEUS and LCR. Accuracy of estimations is in all cases positive (whereas there
212 were negative values in the previous work) and with small standard errors, they are higher
213 than the previous estimates and more coherent with the results of the breeding program. It is
214 especially relevant the change achieved in the pedigree-based EBV for LCR, whose accuracy
215 was -0.05 ± 0.26 and the current one is 0.50 ± 0.07 .

216 These better results may be associated with a stronger data structure (*e.g.* higher number of
217 genotyped rams, closer relationship between reference and candidates to selection). In
218 addition, the current evaluations were done with ssGBLUP, instead of using pseudo-
219 ssGBLUP, avoiding DYD calculation and transmission of inaccuracies to genomic
220 predictions (DYD in dairy sheep are not as accurate as in dairy cattle). Moreover, in these
221 evaluations missing pedigree has been modelled using MF (Legarra et al., 2015), which is
222 more consistent with genomic information. We did some analysis using genetic groups
223 instead of MF and results were not satisfactory, because we obtained more biased evaluations
224 and with smaller slopes (results not shown).

225 The lack of increase of accuracy with genomic evaluations is influenced by the characteristics
226 of the genotyped animals. VanRaden (2008) and Hayes et al. (2009) showed that the increase
227 in accuracy from pedigree to genomic predictions can be explained as “better relationships”.
228 Hayes and collaborators (2009) considered the case of sibships and they showed that extra
229 accuracy is a function of sibship size. In our case, the size of sibships is small (2-3 animals)
230 and thus the expected increase using genomic is small. Moreover, only the rams that went
231 through progeny testing have been genotyped, and these rams were selected based on classical
232 pedigree evaluations (parent average). Selection of siblings is typically avoided to handle
233 genetic diversity. Therefore, the set of genotyped rams and of candidates to selection in the
234 validation population is not a representative sample of all the population. However, this does
235 not hamper GS as in practical GS the breeding scheme would genotype a larger number of
236 half-sibs candidates to selection.

237 Lacaune and MTR reported increases in accuracy using genomic information of 0.15 and 0.16
238 for milk yield, respectively. These results were based on bigger reference populations with
239 1900 and 1000 genotyped animals (Baloche et al., 2014b; Legarra et al., 2014). In fact, the
240 correlation between gain in accuracy and the reference population size (and the heritability of

241 the trait) is known to be high (Daetwyler et al., 2012; Auvray et al., 2014; Goddard, 2009).
242 Moreover, the constitution of a big reference population based on AI rams could be difficult,
243 due to the general low use of AI and the small size of populations. But the decrease in
244 genotyping cost, combining with cheaper low-density chips and imputation methodologies,
245 has brought the possibility to carry on other strategies in order to maximize benefits of
246 genomic information (Rupp et al., 2016) by genotyping natural service rams or genotyping
247 females, for instance. Genotyping other type of animals could be a good strategy and it is
248 planned to be studied in Latxa by a simulation study.

249 In addition, we have done an extra analysis regarding the effect that genomic evaluations may
250 have into lamb selection for AI centre. Currently around 120 lambs of each breed are
251 considered based on their EBV for progeny testing. These lambs come from the 5%
252 genetically best ewes, which have been inseminated by progeny-tested males (CONFELAC,
253 2016). Based on this working procedure, the selected lambs based on EBV or GEBV were
254 compared and no dissimilarities were found, the same animals would be selected by both
255 methodologies. The absence of sibships into the genotyped rams and the limited number of
256 genotyped rams each year is hampering to benefit from the use of genomic information. A
257 bigger genotyping population to preselect AI rams based on genomic values will increase the
258 advantages of the methodology (Aguilar et al., 2010). So, a change in the breeding scheme
259 organization would be necessary, like the proposed by Buisson and collaborators (2014)
260 which provide a 15% increase in AGG in Lacaune breed by genotyping three times the
261 number of lambs required to fulfil the needs of AI centre. Therefore, the implementation of
262 GS needs to be tailored to the specific requirements of the breeding programs (Jonas and de
263 Koning, 2015; Mrode et al., 2018).

264

CONCLUSIONS

265 No clear advantages have been found for GS for Latxa breeds. The characteristics and
266 structure of each breed and breeding scheme are key factors, which determine the possible
267 beneficial effect of genomic information in terms of evaluation accuracy and AGG. We
268 perceive that the number of genotyped animals (all of them AI males) is low and the link
269 between genotyped individuals with phenotypic data and candidates to selection is not strong
270 enough. Therefore, we have to solve these two handicaps before moving toward GS and to
271 have reliable information about how this change would affect to the breeding scheme further
272 studies are planned in Latxa breeds.

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REFERENCES

- 283
- 284 Aguilar, I., I. Misztal, D.L. Johnson, A. Legarra, S. Tsuruta, and T.J. Lawlor. 2010. Hot topic:
285 A unified approach to utilize phenotypic, full pedigree, and genomic information for genetic
286 evaluation of Holstein final score. *J. Dairy Sci.* 93:743–752.
- 287 Auvray, B., J.C. McEwan, S.-A.N. Newman, M. Lee, and K.G. Dodds. 2014. Genomic
288 prediction of breeding values in the New Zealand sheep industry using a 50K SNP chip. *J.*
289 *Anim. Sci.* 92:4375–4389.
- 290 Baloche, G., J.M. Astruc, P. Boulenc, B. Giral-Viala, P. Guibert, P. Panis, A. Legarra, and F.
291 Barillet. 2014a. Genomic selection experiment in Lacaune dairy sheep: progeny test results of
292 rams initially selected either on parent average or on genomic prediction. In: *Proceedings of*
293 *the 10th World Congress of Genetics Applied to Livestock Production*. 17-22 August 2014.
294 Vancouver, Canada.
- 295 Baloche, G., A. Legarra, G. Sallé, H. Larroque, J.M. Astruc, C. Robert-Granié, and F.
296 Barillet. 2014b. Assessment of accuracy of genomic prediction for French Lacaune dairy
297 sheep. *J. Dairy Sci.* 97:1107–1116.
- 298 Bradford, H.L., Y. Masuda, P.M. VanRaden, A. Legarra, and I. Misztal. 2019. Modeling
299 missing pedigree in single-step genomic BLUP. *J. Dairy Sci.* 102:1–11.
- 300 Buisson, D., G. Lagriffoul, G. Baloche, X. Aguerre, P. Boulenc, F. Fidele, G. Frégeat, B.
301 Giral-Viala, P. Guibert, P. Panis, C. Soulas, J.M. Astruc, and F. Barillet. 2014. Genomic
302 breeding schemes in French Lacaune and Manech dairy sheep: design and expected genetic
303 gain. In: *Proceedings of the 10th World Congress of Genetics Applied to Livestock*
304 *Production*. 17-22 August 2014. Vancouver, Canada.
- 305 Christensen, O.F., and M. Lund. 2010. Genomic prediction when some animals are not
306 genotyped. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 42:2.

307 CONFELAC. 2016. Programa de mejora de las razas ovinas Latxa y Carranzana. NEIKER-
308 Tecnia. Granja Modelo de Arkaute. Álava. Spain.

309 Daetwyler, H., A. Swan, J. van der Werf, and B. Hayes. 2012. Accuracy of pedigree and
310 genomic predictions of carcass and novel meat quality traits in multi-breed sheep data
311 assessed by cross-validation. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 44:33.

312 Duchemin, S.I., C. Colombani, A. Legarra, G. Baloché, H. Larroque, J.M. Astruc, F. Barillet,
313 C. Robert-Granié, and E. Manfredi. 2012. Genomic selection in the French Lacaune dairy
314 sheep breed. *J. Dairy Sci.* 95:2723–2733.

315 Forneris, N.S., A. Legarra, Z.G. Vitezica, S. Tsuruta, I. Aguilar, I. Misztal, and R.J.C. Cantet.
316 2015. Quality control of genotypes using heritability estimates of gene content at the marker.
317 *Genetics.* 199: 675–681.

318 Garcia-Baccino, C.A., A. Legarra, O.F. Christensen, I. Misztal, I. Pocrnic, Z.G. Vitezica, and
319 R.J.C. Cantet. 2017. Metafounders are related to F_{st} fixation indices and reduce bias in single-
320 step genomic evaluations. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 49:34.

321 Goddard, M.E. 2009. Genomic selection: Prediction of accuracy and maximisation of long
322 term response. *Genetica (The Hague).* 136:245–257.

323 Hayes, B.J., P.M. Visscher, and M.E. Goddard. 2009. Increased accuracy of artificial
324 selection by using the realized relationship matrix. *Genet. Res., Camb.* 91:47–60.

325 Jonas, E., and D.J. de Koning. 2015. Genomic selection needs to be carefully assessed to meet
326 specific requirements in livestock breeding programs. *Front. Genet.* 6:49.

327 Legarra, A. P. López-Romero, and E. Ugarte 2005. Bayesian model selection of
328 contemporary groups for BLUP genetic evaluation in Latxa dairy sheep. *Livest. Prod. Sci.*
329 93:205–212.

330 Legarra, A., Aguilar, I., and Misztal, I. 2009. A relationship matrix including full pedigree
331 and genomic information. *J. Dairy Sci.* 92:4656–4663.

332 Legarra, A., G. Baloche, F. Barillet, J.M. Astruc, C. Soulas, X. Aguerre, F. Arrese, L.
333 Mintegi, M. Lasarte, F. Maeztu, I. Beltrán de Heredia, and E. Ugarte. 2014. Within- and
334 across-breed genomic predictions and genomic relationships for Western Pyrenees dairy
335 sheep breeds Latxa, Manech, and Basco-Béarnaise. *J. Dairy Sci.* 97:3200–3212.

336 Legarra, A., O.F. Christensen, Z.G. Vitezica, I. Aguilar, and I. Misztal. 2015. Ancestral
337 relationships using metafounders: finite ancestral populations and across population
338 relationships. *Genetics*. 200:455–68.

339 Legarra, A., and A. Reverter. 2018. Semi-parametric estimates of population accuracy and
340 bias of predictions of breeding values and future phenotypes using the LR method. *Genet. Sel.*
341 *Evol.* 50:53.

342 Meyer, K., B. Tier, and A. Swan. 2018. Estimates of genetic trend for single-step genomic
343 evaluations. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 50:39.

344 Misztal, I., S. Tsuruta, T. Strabel, B. Auvray, T. Druet, and D.H. Lee. 2002. BLUPF90 and
345 related programs (BGF90). In: *Proceedings 7th World Congress on Genetics Applied to*
346 *Livestock Production*. 19-23 August 2002. Montpellier, France.

347 Misztal, I., Z.G. Vitezica, A. Legarra, I. Aguilar, and A.A. Swan. 2013. Unknown-parent
348 groups in single-step genomic evaluation. *J. Anim. Breed. Genet.* 130(4):252–258.

349 Mrode, R., G.M. Tarekegn, J.M. Mwacharo, and A. Djikeng 2018. Invited review: Genomic
350 selection for small ruminants in developed countries: how applicable for the rest of the world?
351 *Animal*. 1333–1340.

352 Pszczola, M., H.A. Mulder, and M.P.L. Calus. 2011. Effect of enlarging the reference
353 population with (un)genotyped animals on the accuracy of genomic selection in dairy cattle. *J.*
354 *Dairy Sci.* 94:431–441.

355 Pszczola, M., T. Strabel, H.A. Mulder, and M.P.L. Calus. 2012. Reliability of direct genomic
356 values for animals with different relationships within and to the reference population. *J. Dairy*
357 *Sci.* 95:389–400.

358 Quaas, R. L. 1988. Additive genetic model with groups and relationships. *J. Dairy Sci.*
359 71:1338–1345.

360 Rupp, R., S. Mucha, H. Larroque, J. McEwan, and J. Conington. 2016. Genomic application
361 in sheep and goat breeding. *Anim. Front.* 6:39–44.

362 Shumbusho, F., J. Raoul, J.M. Astruc, I. Palhiere, and J.M. Elsen. 2013. Potential benefits of
363 genomic selection on genetic gain of small ruminant breeding programs. *J. Anim. Sci.*
364 91:3644–3657.

365 Ugarte, E., E. Urarte, F. Arrese, J. Arranz, L. Silio and C. Rodríguez. 1996. Genetic
366 parameters and trends for milk production of blond-faced Latxa sheep using Bayesian
367 analysis. *J. Dairy Sci.* 79:2268–2277.

368 VanRaden, P.M. 2008. Efficient methods to compute genomic predictions. *J. Dairy Sci.*
369 91:4414–4423.

370 VanRaden, P.P., C.P. Van Tassell, G.R. Wiggans, T.S. Sonstegard, R.D. Schnabel, J.F.
371 Taylor, and F.S. Schenkel. 2009. Invited review: Reliability of genomic predictions for North
372 American Holstein bulls. *J. Dairy Sci.* 92:16–24.

373 Vitezica, Z.G., I. Aguilar, I. Misztal, and A. Legarra. 2011. Bias in genomic predictions for
374 populations under selection. *Genet. Res., Camb.* 93:357–366.

Table 1: Description of the phenotypic and pedigree data (milk yield in 120 days of lactation) included in the study; for Latxa Cara Negra from Euskadi (LCNEUS) and Latxa Cara Rubia (LCR).

Data (1984-2017)	Breed	
	LCNEUS	LCR
No. animals in pedigree	263308	150185
% animals with data and complete genealogy	22.28	35.30
No. phenotypic records	639517	392109
No. ♀ in data	235360	133230
No. Flocks	456	325
No. AI ♂ with progeny in data	1883	1837

375

Table 2: Number of rams distributed across categories, year of birth and average daughter number with lactations in the whole data set per genotyped ram; for Latxa Cara Negra from Euskadi (LCNEUS) and Latxa Cara Rubia (LCR).

Breed	Rams in training group, AI progeny tested				Rams in validation group, AI progeny tested		
	No. genotyped	No. non- genotyped	Birth years	Average daughters	No. genotyped	Birth years	Average daughters
LCNEUS	216	1401	1984- 2011	54.04	59	2012- 2014	21.32
LCR	202	1305	1983- 2011	67.53	91	2012- 2014	30.54

376

Table 3: Considering validation rams, number of validation sires or maternal grandsires genotyped or non-genotyped; for Latxa Cara Negra from Euskadi (LCNEUS) and Latxa Cara Rubia (LCR).

Breed	No. rams in validation group	No. sire in training group		No. maternal grandsire in training group	
		Genotyped	Non-genotyped	Genotyped	Non-genotyped
LCNEUS	59	31	25	18	36
LCR	91	43	46	16	67

377

Table 4: Considering validation rams, number of full-sib rams, number of sires, sires with one or more than one ram and rate of rams per sire; for Latxa Cara Negra from Euskadi (LCNEUS) and Latxa Cara Rubia (LCR).

Breed	No. rams in validation group	No. full-sib rams	No. sires		Rams/Sire
			With one ram	With > one ram	
LCNEUS	59	2	20	8	2.95
LCR	91	2	36	22	2.53

378

Table 5: Bias, slope and accuracy \pm standard errors (by bootstrap) of pedigree and genomic evaluations and their difference (genomic-pedigree); for Latxa Cara Negra from Euskadi (LCNEUS) and Latxa Cara Rubia (LCR).

Breed	Methodology	Bias	Slope	$\rho_{w,p}$
LCNEUS	Pedigree	1.41 \pm 6.41	0.96 \pm 0.20	0.55 \pm 0.09
	Genomic	5.62 \pm 5.52	0.82 \pm 0.17	0.56 \pm 0.08
	Genomic-pedigree	4.21 \pm 2.63	-0.14 \pm 0.08	0.01 \pm 0.04
LCR	Pedigree	7.66 \pm 6.06	0.68 \pm 0.12	0.50 \pm 0.07
	Genomic	11.74 \pm 5.32	0.57 \pm 0.10	0.51 \pm 0.07
	Genomic-pedigree	4.08 \pm 2.55	-0.11 \pm 0.05	0.01 \pm 0.04

379

Supplementary Table 1: Γ matrix estimates for MF, defined from 1985 to 2015 every 3 years; for Latxa Cara Negra from Euskadi (LCNEUS).

	MF1	MF2	MF3	MF4	MF5	MF6	MF7	MF8	MF9	MF10	MF11
MF1	0.632	0.259	0.384	0.417	0.476	0.465	0.437	0.442	0.410	0.410	0.410
MF2	0.259	1.027	0.392	0.316	0.335	0.363	0.312	0.358	0.349	0.349	0.349
MF3	0.384	0.392	0.843	0.352	0.392	0.417	0.397	0.406	0.393	0.393	0.393
MF4	0.417	0.316	0.352	0.848	0.456	0.365	0.395	0.401	0.380	0.380	0.380
MF5	0.476	0.335	0.392	0.456	0.768	0.415	0.397	0.413	0.390	0.390	0.390
MF6	0.465	0.363	0.417	0.365	0.415	0.863	0.394	0.388	0.393	0.393	0.393
MF7	0.437	0.312	0.397	0.395	0.397	0.394	0.995	0.295	0.356	0.356	0.356
MF8	0.442	0.358	0.406	0.401	0.413	0.388	0.295	0.894	0.338	0.338	0.338
MF9	0.410	0.349	0.393	0.380	0.390	0.393	0.356	0.338	0.858	0.356	0.356
MF10	0.410	0.349	0.393	0.380	0.390	0.393	0.356	0.338	0.356	0.858	0.356
MF11	0.410	0.349	0.393	0.380	0.390	0.393	0.356	0.338	0.356	0.356	0.858

Supplementary Table 2: Γ matrix estimates for MF, defined from 1985 to 2015 every 3 years for Spanish progeny and every 9 years for French origin; for Latxa Cara Rubia (LCR).

	MF1	MF2	MF3	MF4	MF5	MF6	MF7	MF8	MF9	MF10	MF11	MF12	MF13	MF14
MF1	0.681	0.258	0.309	0.394	0.433	0.424	0.454	0.446	0.450	0.443	0.322	0.373	0.429	0.442
MF2	0.258	1.053	0.308	0.358	0.225	0.359	0.376	0.380	0.383	0.376	0.242	0.332	0.380	0.364
MF3	0.309	0.308	1.034	0.337	0.302	0.294	0.356	0.363	0.364	0.372	0.265	0.310	0.371	0.353
MF4	0.394	0.358	0.337	0.908	0.402	0.444	0.450	0.431	0.434	0.409	0.297	0.383	0.398	0.406
MF5	0.433	0.225	0.302	0.402	0.827	0.419	0.416	0.415	0.427	0.408	0.290	0.438	0.433	0.429
MF6	0.424	0.359	0.294	0.444	0.419	0.785	0.446	0.419	0.435	0.414	0.293	0.446	0.428	0.428
MF7	0.454	0.376	0.356	0.450	0.416	0.446	0.667	0.464	0.461	0.435	0.317	0.468	0.454	0.459
MF8	0.446	0.380	0.363	0.431	0.415	0.419	0.464	0.599	0.463	0.436	0.318	0.464	0.460	0.468
MF9	0.450	0.383	0.364	0.434	0.427	0.435	0.461	0.463	0.565	0.467	0.312	0.479	0.472	0.469
MF10	0.443	0.376	0.372	0.409	0.408	0.414	0.435	0.436	0.467	0.613	0.322	0.476	0.480	0.472
MF11	0.322	0.242	0.265	0.297	0.290	0.293	0.317	0.318	0.312	0.322	1.450	0.327	0.339	0.317
MF12	0.373	0.332	0.310	0.383	0.438	0.446	0.468	0.464	0.479	0.476	0.327	0.678	0.483	0.483
MF13	0.429	0.380	0.371	0.398	0.433	0.428	0.454	0.460	0.472	0.480	0.339	0.483	0.579	0.506
MF14	0.442	0.364	0.353	0.406	0.429	0.428	0.459	0.468	0.469	0.472	0.317	0.483	0.506	0.601

Figure 1: Rams used in artificial insemination by year of birth and the distribution of the genotyped individuals, for Latxa Cara Negra from Euskadi (LCNEUS) and Latxa Cara Rubia (LCR).